

BD FACSDiva 8.0.1

Tube: NTSR1

Population	#Events	%Parent	%Total
All Events	200,000	####	100.0
nucleii	97,368	48.7	48.7
P1	57,359	58.9	28.7
P2	54,694	95.4	27.3
++	1,669	3.1	0.8